

IS JOURNALISM EDUCATION IN INDIA ON RIGHT TRACK?

Dr. Manisha Prakash

Abstract

Eronnini Megwa (2001) and Carey (2000) of the US argue that journalism education is an education for democracy. This speaks of the importance of Journalism as a course for humanity. Well-trained journalists are integral to functioning democracies like India. Training in this discipline is over seventy years old here and it has grown considerably in the past decade but it is yet to become result oriented and purposeful. Scholars have rightly felt that general instructions and classroom lectures are bookish and bereft of practical demonstration. There is no agreement on what direction Mass Communication education should take. Theoretical input overpowers adequate practically relevant components and inputs. In this paper, the present status and relevance of journalism education in India is explored based on primary and secondary data collected through personal observations and interviews of journalism students – past and present.

Key words: Journalism education, media studies, journalism curriculum

INTRODUCTION

Journalism education across India has been undergoing dramatic changes with the increasing demand for competent workforce in the booming media business. Education in the field of Mass Communication and Journalism in India made its advent through western influences. Teaching in this stream assumes new significance in the age of globalization and communication. There was a time when no formal training was required to be a journalist in this country. There are generations of reporters and editors who joined this trade because they had a flair for writing or speaking. Many still believe that journalists are born and not made. But with introduction of the discipline of Mass Communication in Indian Universities, those taking these courses hold a better chance to get

their career started. But the truth is very few Journalism colleges are able to produce industry ready professionals. There is a huge rush to get admission in journalism courses in Indian institutions though quality is a casualty all through.

Notably, it was India which strongly articulated during the 1970s for a New World Information and Communication Order (NWICO). But the country is yet to take any strong follow up action in the academic aspects of education in communication subsequently. Consequently, course contents have not changed substantially nor the books of journalism. The need for books to reflect national realities has not been met with yet. Whatever books are available, they are with American orientation which does not bear relevance to the Indian situation.

JOURNALISM STUDIES IN INDIA

There is no accurate documentation of the historical trajectory of journalism education in India (Muppiddi, 2008). Most of the beginners training for journalists occurred on the job. It was only in the 1950s that courses in journalism were started in colleges. As per Eapen (1991), the Hislop Christian College at Nagpur University was the first to set up a journalism department in 1952-53. Eapen is also considered the first person to document that the American media experts and expertise had left an indelible impression on the genesis and the growth of Indian Journalism and Mass Communication (1991). The Central Government's Indian Institute of Mass Communication, New Delhi, which was established in 1965, was conceptualized by Wilber Schramm and a team of American experts. Despite being in existence for over five decades, the Institute has not been able to enrich indigenous scholarship considerably as was also pointed by Eapen.

The second generation developments in the history of journalism education are said to have begun post 1960s. According to Krishnatray (as cited by Sundeep R Muppidi: 2008), the earlier certificate courses in journalism and mass communication were replaced by university based journalism departments which offered

one or two year degrees in journalism and mainly had the students from the urban middle class. He added that these departments contributed to the growing economy of the country by offering programmes which included subjects like reporting, editing besides history of journalism. It was during this time, the departments changed the nomenclature from simple 'journalism' to 'journalism and mass communication'. Further subjects like communication, advertising and public relations were also added. According to Eapen (1991) there were only six university departments up to 1961 in India and the number went up to 25 by 1981 (Sundeeep R Muppidi, 2008). Later a number of Universities came up with journalism and mass communication departments (Kavita Karant, 2001). Post liberalization, a number of private institutes, mainly autonomous or recognized by the University Grants Commission (UGC), private Universities (established under state laws), institutes and deemed Universities came into existence (C.S.H.N. Murthy, Manipal University, 2010). According to Krishantray (2008), these are the fourth generation and latest establishments in journalism and mass communication.

The journalism education has also turned into a business, as Sainath (2001) termed it as 'Corporatization', with ISO 9000 and ISO 14000 coming to play a prominent role which these institutions sought to show as following international standards in the institutional maintenance and appearance for attracting the international community. Foreign students show willingness to study in these institutes, as education for foreigners is cheap whereas for Indians it is dear given a very high fee structure.

Today, the NDTV, the India TV, the Times Now, Marwah Films among others have started their own media schools. We also have a Bennett University by the Benett Coleman & Co. Ltd. This is the latest trend in journalism education which has brought about a corporate feel to it.

A number of central, state and private university journalism departments/schools are providing undergraduate (Bachelor of

Arts – BA/ Bachelor of Mass Communication – BMC), and post graduate (MJMC) degrees or Diplomas in journalism and Mass Communication. In addition, a significant number of universities in India are also providing MPhil and PhD degrees.

POSSIBLE ISSUES WITH JOURNALISM EDUCATION

Despite this progress, education in journalism and mass communication in India has been stagnant and alienated from the industrial and academic needs. A major flaw is said to be the fact that there is no direct linkage between the industry and the education in media, however the need for such linkage is always disputable. The media industry feels the training offered in these centres is inadequate. The industry does not find it feasible to conduct campus selection for the reason that the students do not display the appropriate skills necessary for them to be taken as journalists. In India the Universities State and Central, besides private educational institutions have failed to formulate a common core curriculum with relevance to the fast changing industry (Murthy, 2010).

Considering the present scenario, several questions arise as to what should be the curriculum for the current generation of journalism students and how should one endeavour to bring a balance between the academics and the industry. It is necessary to find out the extent to which undergraduate colleges and graduate colleges of mass communication and journalism in India are following a curriculum that is relevant to the changing technological developments both abroad and in India in the wake of globalization and privatization. Current problems pursuing the media education in India and the methods which could be seen as possible way outs to improve the situation to some extent needs to be discussed. The knowledge and skills critical for students to become successful professionals need to be identified as well as the characteristics that would elevate media education to a professional status without criticism from the industry. There is an agreement of the view that as the admissions in the private institutions and sometime also in the government institutions are generally not based on merit and proper evaluation

of creative talents (in the fields of writing, general knowledge and speaking), at present there is a low quality output of performance from these students at the time of passing out from their institutions.

“The vehicle of journalism education seems to be halted with punctured wheels (Desai, 2008)”. There is a need to look for an appropriate model. South Asian educators train journalism students with borrowed curricula from the West (Ullah, 2014)

The whole education system of journalism and mass communication in India is afflicted with a number of maladies. Most institutions suffer from lack of adequately qualified faculty as the government process of recruitment is slow and courses are run mostly by guest faculty who are paid pitiable amounts. Most institutions enrol students who are not fit for any category of media either by aptitude or by attitude. In the absence of a standard process of admission, seats are filled for the sake of it which is in flagrant violation of the stipulated rules for admission of students and recruitment of faculty by the University Grants Commission (UGC). Excessive admissions, violating the natural and normal ratio of teacher: pupil in a class room, coupled with poor and abysmally low infrastructure, further diluted the quality of teaching.

There is a general agreement that there is a need to change the present curriculum and the treatment of curriculum of journalism and mass communication in India should be multi task oriented rather than industry focused. The media educators are of the opinion that by merely allowing media schools to be overshadowed by the industry may leave the vast academic potential of this powerful branch of social science and arts underutilized and even unexploited for the needs of developing countries in the post globalization era, which is not advisable.

The media industry often seeks to promote an emphasis on skills in preference over liberal education (Tapas Ray (2007). It has been debated whether journalism programmes should focus almost entirely on professional skills, or should superimpose these skills over a broad liberal arts education . “Even today some in the

journalism industry pressure j-schools to put more emphasis on skills and mechanics, especially as the profession becomes more dependent on technology” (Kunkel. T, 2002). We cannot have a course curricula in journalism and mass communication tilted in favor of imparting just basic skills required for the industry. Sainath (2001) is not in favor of reforming curriculum only to cater the corporate sector. Kunkel recommends that journalists must be strong critical thinkers who know enough about geography, history and the human condition to understand why events play out as they do. They ought to have a world view' (2002). “The ultimate objective of the journalism education should be to improve the practice of journalism not only by training skilled practitioners but also by teaching how journalism impinges on other areas of public life and illustrates critical social issues (Reese, 1999).”

The present system of imparting education in journalism and mass communication in all papers is tedious, boring and not in keeping with the requirements of the industry. One who has a mental disposition for video production, yet he/she has to study print media reporting, editing, subbing, advertising and radio production. Another model of study could be developed which gives students a choice, hands-on training as well as internship opportunities.

The quality of admissions is basically very low and the students taking admission in journalism course are those who could not get admitted in other streams. It reminds of what Sunanda Datta K Ray (2000) said, that if someone was not qualified for any job, he became a journalist. Very few would join straight with meritorious background with an aptitude for journalism and mass communication. Others in spite of three years of education would not be in a position to speak or write English and Hindi fluently therefore making them unfit either

Methodology

A survey method has been employed to determine student's views on the effectiveness of journalism education in India. Survey

questions were sent to journalism students of both private and government colleges in India known to the researcher through whatsapp. Some of the students also forwarded the questions to other journalism students. The students were based in Patna, Ranchi, Pune, Mumbai, Jammu and Noida. Respondents sent back their opinions in response to the questionnaire sent to them. Of these maximum were from Patna. However, only 27 replies could be received. The obtained data was analyzed using simple analytical method.

Research Questions

1. Are you satisfied with the journalism course offered in universities?
2. What do you think is missing in the journalism course?
3. Does the course prepares a student taking it for a career of his/her choice?

Results and Discussion

The respondents' views offered a range of similarities. When asked about the satisfaction level with the journalism course offered in universities, sixteen students said that they were not satisfied while four said they were partly satisfied. However, seven expressed satisfaction with their universities/institutions. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1: Satisfaction level of students with the course offered in

their institutions

When asked about what was missing in the journalism course, twenty three students said that practical exposure was badly missing from the course. Two students said that the course needs updating. One said that students should also be taught in Hindi. Some students also pointed out about the lack of placement opportunities and the poor teaching.

Students' comments

1. Teaching is limited to books. The college claims to provide job opportunities but it is not true. There is no campus interview leaving the student confused in the end whether they have done the right thing by opting for a course in journalism.
2. More practical classes are required so that students can learn and understand better.
3. The course needs to be based on skill enhancement.
4. The course only helps in passing exams and does not prepare for the professional world.
5. The course should be job oriented and provide job training as it is a vocational course.
6. The course needs to be updated.
7. Some teachers give notes from the internet which they fail to explain leaving the students on their own to decipher its meaning.

To find out whether the journalism course is making the students career ready, a third and final question was asked. Eleven students said that the course prepares them for a career while seven said it did not and another seven said it prepares them only partly. However, two students said that it all depends on the student and how he/she takes the course. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Career preparedness through Journalism course

Findings

1. Students are not satisfied with the journalism course offered in universities.
2. Practical classes and real exposure is missing from the curriculum.
3. There is confusion among students on whether the course prepares them for a career.

Conculsion

The nature of journalism education in India has changed over the past decade .The research finds out about the failure of conventional west-oriented or readymade curricula. There is a necessity for a new approach to form a model curriculum. However, the research also brings up many questions. It will be worthwhile to understand the reasons behind 'unsatisfactory' performance of the institutes of journalism. It will be necessary to systematically explain the real causes behind this while at the same time make a comparative study of the successful and the unsuccessful centres of journalism teaching. Success would encompass placement, teaching

methodology, course curriculum, faculty and facilities available for students. There is also a need to look at the challenges in teaching journalism in the present times in India. It has also been pointed out that private institutes of Journalism are nothing but money minting centres ill-equipped to train students in this field. The training is carried out in both government and private colleges without quality training material and with no orientation towards media needs. The industry demands journalists proficient in multimedia skills. Universities and institutions are finding it difficult to meet these challenges.

As the curricula is not fit with the local context, Journalism graduates are being undervalued in the local media recruitment process. The ignorance of the native industry requirements and the flaws of the west-centric curricula suggest that the Indian Journalism institutions require a different approach to course contents.

References

- Desai, M. K. (2008). Reviewing Communication/ Media Education in India: Many players, diverse directions but lost focus?, *Journal of Global Communication*, 1 (2),118-131.
- Eapen, K.E. (1991): Journalism Education and Text books in SAARC Countries. www.uta.fi/textbooks/India_saarc.html
- Kavita, K. (2001): Journalism Education in India. *Journalism Studies*, 1469-9699, Volume 2, Issue 2, 2001, Pages 281-299.
- Kunkel, T. (2002): Journalism requires wide exposure: liberal arts or trade skills? Students need both. *The Quill*, 90. 6 p. 17 (2). Quoted from Murthy, 2010
- Reese, S.D. (1999): The Progressive Potential of Journalism Education: Recasting the Academic versus Professional Debate. *The Harvard International Journal of Press Politics*. 4.4 pp 70-94.

Shakuntala, R. (2009). GLOCALIZATION OF INDIAN JOURNALISM, *Journalism Studies*, 10:4, 474-488, DOI: 10.1080/14616700802618563

Sundeeep, R., Muppidi. (2008). Journalism Education in India, *Media Asia*, 35:2, 67-83, DOI: 10.1080/01296612.2008.11726871

Ullah, Mohammad S. (2014). China Media Research. *China Media Research*. 10. 15-23.

